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Silencing the Lambs: The Aftermath of English-Only Initiatives in the United States

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The imposition of Proposition 227 in California back in 1998 has caused various controversies on the state's reception and attitude towards bilingualism and bilingual education. The proposition requires California public schools to teach Limited English Proficiency (LEP) students in special classes that are nearly or exclusively taught in English, leading to the elimination of bilingual classes (Kinney). This paper therefore rests on the argument that English-only initiatives, such as the Proposition 227, have brought bigger problems than solutions in the hopes of academically aiding minority students or heritage language learners. As such, there is a need to revisit and review the effects of imposing English-exclusive learning programs in many states in America. English-only programs, including the Proposition 227, have increased coercive rather than cooperative relations in educating language minority students (Mora). Hence, public policy making that limits the legitimate participation and unrecognizes the interests of minority groups is utterly destabilizing a culturally and linguistically diverse nation such as the United States. This paper is also anchored on four (4) discussion points on the aftermath of English-only initiatives in the lives of minority students (English learners) and their families; namely, the hegemony of English and its danger on native languages; the destruction of minority students' cultural identities due to English-only programs; the proven and justified benefits of biliteracy as bilingualism's handmaiden; and lastly, English learners' attitudes and perspectives toward English-only policy (EOP).

Perhaps the most underwhelming and disappointing impact of English-only initiatives would be the loss of minority students' native languages and cultural identities. Due to the need for immigrant children to overcome racial boundaries, cultural difference, and linguistic barriers to be more "Americanized," they fall victims to the hegemony of English and the Anglo-American culture. As highlighted in a research article written by Cohen and Wickens, "English-only policies promote subtractive bilingualism where immigrant students learn English at the expense of losing their first language" (12). Immigrant students see the importance placed upon English as the status language compared to their native languages which are

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usually undervalued or frowned upon. Hence, they have no choice because the hegemony of English in American economic and cultural life is so pervasive (Crawford). This causes immigrant students to reject their native languages and prefer to live their lives speaking in English.

Similarly, English-only initiatives are destroying the cultural identities of English learners, or those whose native language is not English. Rachel Hazlehurst, an advocate of bilingual education writes, "If there's a disconnect between students' home identities...and what's promoted by the school, students are more likely to disconnect, disinvest, and experience educational failure" (Anderson). This speaks strongly of the danger English-only policies pose not only on English learners' education but also on their lives, as the loss of one's native language is the loss of his or her cultural identity. Consequently, promoting English-only programs in schools negatively affects students' relationship with their families, as they choose not to speak or communicate with their parents, since the latter hardly speak and understand the second language. Unfortunately, immigrant students always notice that although they have learned how to speak in English, they end up disowning their cultural heritage, while developing feelings of shame and prejudice towards anything related to their cultural roots (Cohen and Wickens 9).

On a positive note, instead of immersing language minority students to English-only programs, it would be more beneficial for them if their teachers would advocate for the development of their biliteracy. Experts in the field of education are also looking at biliteracy to help minority students gain invaluable academic skills and strengthen their overall language competency in two languages. Yambi found that, "acquiring literacy in the native language provides clear benefits for English learners who are learning English. This is through the use of cognates when reading for comprehension in another language" (Cohen et al. 21). Aside from the fact that it is easier to learn literacy in one's native language, another benefit of biliteracy is, when native language literacy is developed, literacy in another language would come naturally. An empirical study has proven that biliteracy is an asset rather than a liability in both elementary and secondary levels. Giambo and Szecsi found that, "at both the elementary and secondary levels, English learners who received literacy instruction in both their native language and English performed better in English reading than English learners who were taught solely in English" (22). Above all, for me, the most striking benefit of biliteracy to minority students would be the fact that bilingual and biliterate children have more divergent and creative thinking abilities in terms of solving problems (Baker 23).

Unlike the many failures of English-only programs in the U.S., I am truly grateful to see, this time, that in terms of the discourse about bilingualism and biliteracy, there are more positive opinions and good research findings than unpleasant ones. But this may not be entirely consistent when English learners are asked about their attitudes and perspectives toward the implementation of English-only policies in their schools. For instance, Shvidko reported in her study that, "English learners both have positive and negative attitudes toward the implementation of English-only policy in

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higher education" (12). The result, arguably, may refute the conclusive statements from many experts in the field that English-only programs have nothing beneficial to give English learners or minority students. It is also interesting to note that the English learners who participated in Shvidko's research agreed that the EOP in their university helped them learn more about the language and easily adjust in their new academic environment. However, the pervasive bleakness of English-only initiatives is still undeniable and impossible to cover up. English learners have more negative attitudes and cynical perspectives toward EOP than positives ones. They include, teachers' negative reception on students who are using their first language outside the classroom, the punishments given to students when they underperform in their English classes, the unconditional character of the policy that denied learners their agency, and the lack of systematic implementation.

Issues of race, color, and culture have always been hotly debated in the United States; and the belief that minority students should only be educated in English stems from these complications. The many problems of English-only programs in America warrant critical analysis, as it is not only about the education of minority students, but the loss of their native languages and cultural identities as well. The status quo leads us to realizing the need to act on this matter and call the attention of both educators and legislators in every state to abandon the "English-only" perspective, as it has become so pervasive and detrimental in the lives of minority groups. To patch up the damages contributed by these English-only initiatives, such as the Proposition 227 in California, we need to advocate for a more inclusive and nurturing American education for minority students through the right implementation of bilingual education programs. Further, we must aim to promote the development of biliteracy even at the early years of schooling, as various research studies conclude that being bilingual and biliterate leads to academic progress. However, nothing is perfect in this world and genuine educational reforms do not happen overnight. The two main questions to answer now are, "How do we effectively implement bilingual education?" and "What languages to cater in dual language programs?" To answer these questions, we begin with the concept of accountability. To concretize accountability in the context of an effective bilingual education program, "responsibilities for student success should be clear and have been shared with all school personnel" (Villareal and Solis). This means that program leaders are well aware about the dynamics of bilingual education and share an active commitment to bilingualism, teachers feel supported in schools and are empowered to fulfill their duties and responsibilities through provisions of relevant trainings, for them to be more reflective and become action researchers, parents and other stakeholders feel welcome and play different roles (leadership, resource, decision making) in the bilingual education process. Moreover, families of students from minority groups are given a voice and space in the education of their children, free from racial judgments and biases. When all these key players become fully accountable on their roles in the implementation of bilingual education programs, English language learners in the U.S., surely, will never be left behind. Academic

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success will also be within the students' reach. As regards the languages to cater in dual language programs, parents and families and even students themselves should have the final say. Effective bilingual education does not rest on entertaining bandwagons or what the majority think and feel. It works best when each student in the classroom, regardless of whether he or she is the only speaker of a specific language, is given the opportunity to develop academically in both his or her native language and English. Indeed, it is high time that we all responsibly cement the space of bilingual education in every American school!

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